

Effect of bush burning Intensity on selected soil physical and chemical properties in Ile-Ife, Nigeria

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Abstract

Bush burning for land clearing is prevalent among small-holder farmers in Nigeria. Though an age long practice, few empirical studies have documented its impact on soil physical properties. This study investigated the effects of controlled bush burning on selected soil physical and chemical properties over two distinct cropping seasons. Three treatments consisting of two fire intensities (burning at 200°C and 400°C) and a control with each treatment replicated four times were arranged in Randomized Complete Block Design. The temperature was measured with an infrared thermometer. Soil particle size was not affected by burning at both fire intensities, while surface (0-15 cm) soil bulk density decreased from 1.43 gcm⁻³ to 1.095 gcm⁻³ after controlled burning. Soil water repellency was not affected by the treatment while sorptivity decreased significantly but soil pH improved from 5.3 to 7.03 as fire intensity increased from 200°C to 400°C. Soil strength reduced after burning from mean value of 7.05 kgm⁻² in control to 5.99 kgm⁻² at 400°C fire intensity. Microaggregate stability, soil organic carbon and total nitrogen contents decreased while exchangeable bases and available phosphorus contents increased as fire intensity increased from 200°C to 400°C. In conclusion, within the period under consideration, fire intensity only improved bulk density, soil strength, pH, and exchangeable bases.

Keywords: Controlled Bush burning; Fire intensities; Soil properties

Introduction

Bush burning is one of the land clearing methods used in Southwestern Nigeria by farmers prior to planting. Before desired crops are planted by farmers, several land-clearing management practices are employed including of fire to burn off dried plant residues. The fallow vegetation is slashed, left to dry and burnt before crop cultivation (Hauser and Norgrove, 2001). This practice is prevalent among farmers in Nigeria and has been recognized as an essential part of traditional shifting cultivation normally called 'slash and burn agriculture' (Onwueme, 1978). Majority of low-input farmers in Nigeria practice bush burning with little or no knowledge about the consequent effect of such practice on the

soil. Studies by Heydari *et al.* (2012) revealed that the most damaging agent to soil and vegetation in the Zagros forest of Iran is Fire. Bush burning has tremendous influence on soil properties including the physical and chemical properties. Influence of bush burning on soil physical properties include an increase in soil compaction which leads to decrease in infiltration capacity, increased surface runoff which exacerbates soil erosion (Soto and Diaz-Fierros, 1998); (Doerr *et al.*, 2000), and also leads to soil water repellency (Mataix-Solera *et al.*, 2012).

Bush burning also causes the volatilization of soil nitrogen (Giovannini and Lucchesi, 1997), conversion of the organic phosphorus pool to orthophosphate

(Cade-Menun *et al.*, 2000), a significant increase in soil cation concentration (Rau *et al.*, 2009) and overall increase in fertility level of soil (Dlapa *et al.*, 2014; Martin *et al.*, 2012). However, one factor that determines the role fire plays on soil properties including physical and chemical properties is the intensity of fire during burning. Bushfire intensity refers to the amount of heat it generates during burning. Determination of soil status with regards to its nutrient losses response is controlled by fire intensity (Andreu *et al.*, 1994). Robichaud *et al.* (2008) reported that influence bush burning have on properties of soil is highly variable and that one of the important determinants of this effect is the fire intensity. It is influenced by vegetation, weather and topography, or shape of the land (Cary *et al.*, 2006). Neary *et al.* (1999) observed that physical and chemical changes occur at high temperatures with the aggregation of silt and clay into sand-sized entities at temperatures greater than 220°C, and that distillation of organic matter occurs between 200°C and 315°C while nutrient volatilization occurs between 200°C and 400°C. Certini (2005) reported two categories of fires: wildfires and controlled fires. Any fire that is monitored and diligently supervised to meet pre-determined land management objectives is called controlled fire (Stacey, 2012). This type of fire is normally at low intensity and applied when soil is moderately moist, while wildfires are uncontrolled with the presence of massive fuel loads and have high intensity.

Fire intensity is classified into three; 1) Low intensity: it utilized a maximum burning temperatures of 100°C to 250°C, the soil surface is characterized by black ashes, scorched litters and low plant mortality. 2)

Moderate intensity: the burning temperatures is between 300°C and 400°C, it results into consumption of most of the plant materials. It ultimately lead to the exposure of the bare soil surface. 3) High intensity: it uses burning temperature in excess of 500°C thereby producing white ash which can be recognized after the complete combustion of heavy fuel. It lead to the reddening of the soil due to the transformation of Fe-oxides and removal of organic matter completely (Certini, 2005). A blackened layer usually underlain soil making it severely reddened in the burnt area was reported by (Eckmeier *et al.*, 2013).

Several authors have reported the effects of wildfires on soil properties in different regions of the world including the Mediterranean ecosystems (Uribe *et al.*, 2013; Goberna *et al.*, 2012; Mataix-Solera *et al.*, 2012). However, few authors have reported the impacts of controlled bush burning on soil properties as influenced by varying fire intensities and most especially in southwestern Nigeria. Therefore, the objectives of this study were to determine the effects of varying fire intensity on selected soil physical and chemical properties.

Materials and Methods

Description of the study site

The field experiment was carried out at the Obafemi Awolowo University Teaching and Research Farm, Ile-Ife, Osun State in Southwestern Nigeria. The study area lies between approximately Latitudes 7° 32'N & 7° 33'N and Longitudes 4° 32'E & 4° 34'E with an altitude of about 244 m above mean sea level. It is in the rainforest ecosystem of Southwestern region of Nigeria with mean annual rainfall of 1500 mm which is bimodally distributed and having its peak in

June and September. Coarse grained granite and gneiss is the parent material of soils in the experimental site and it was locally classified as Iwo series (Okusami and Oyediran, 1985) and as Ultisol which at subgroup level have argillic or kandic horizon and a relatively low content of bases with base saturation less than 35% at 2 m depth or 75 cm below a fragipan. They typically have an ochric epipedon, and are mostly formed under forest vegetation. The surface texture vary from sandy loam to sandy clay loam and the soil to be well-drained.

Experimental design

The experiment was laid out in a Randomized Complete Block Design. Three treatments were applied consisting of two fire intensities (burning at 200°C and 400°C) and a control, each of which was replicated four times. The bush cover which comprised of guinea grass (*Panicum maximum*) on the experimental site was cleared and left on the plots to dry. Calibration study was done to determine the temperature produced by a given weight of the dried plant biomass carefully arranged inside a sack. Two weights were chosen, one produced approximately 200°C (4 kg/m²) and the second produced approximately 400°C (8 kg/m²). The dried plant residue was carefully arranged on the soil in each plot except on the control. The dried plant residues were burnt on each plot separately. An infra-red thermometer was used to measure the temperature of fire at the center of the flame on each plot while the plant residues were allowed to burn completely on the soil. Soil samples were taken from each plot before the burning and a day after. Analysis of selected soil physical and chemical properties was

carried out after soil samples were transferred to the laboratory. The experiment was carried out in two cropping seasons. First season was conducted in April, 2016 while the Second season was in August, 2016. Soil samples were taken from each plot in the two season's pre and post burning. The soil samples were collected from the top 15 cm of the profile. Samples collected were air-dried and passed through a 2 mm mesh.

Duration of study.

The experiment was carried out in two distinct periods during the 2016 cropping year. The study area has two bimodal distinct seasons of high rainfall between March and July while the second season of less rainfall occurs between late August and November. Sandwiched between these two periods is the August break.

Soil field determinations.

Soil strength

A dynamic cone penetrometer (UK DCP 2.2) with 20 mm cone diameter and 60 degree angle was used to measure soil strength. The result obtained was read and recorded on the meter rule after several blows were made until a penetration depth of 50 cm was reached. A core sampler was used to determine the soil bulk density. The soil collected using the core sampler was weighed on a weighing balance and the weight was recorded. The soil was then oven dried at 105°C until a constant weight was obtained. Estimation of bulk density was done by dividing the oven-dry mass of soil by the bulk soil volume. Soil microaggregate stability was determined using the method described by (Igwe and Nkemakusi, 2007) and (Sung, 2012). In this method, Water-dispersible clay (WDC) and

water-dispersible silt (WDS) were used to assess the microaggregate stability with the following formula:

$$\frac{\%(WDS + WDC)}{\% \text{ total silt and clay}} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Unsaturated hydraulic conductivity

The decagon mini disk infiltrometer was used to determine the unsaturated (infiltration) hydraulic conductivity *in situ*. The infiltrometer was adjusted to a suction of 2 cm for the determinations. The porous stainless steel contact was firmly placed on the soil to have a good contact with the soil surface. Water was filled inside the infiltrometer reservoir. The infiltration rate was taken every thirty (30) seconds for five minutes. The method proposed by (Zhang, 1997) was used to determine the unsaturated (infiltration) hydraulic conductivity by measuring the cumulative infiltration versus time and fitting the results with the infiltration function as:

$$C_1t + C_2\sqrt{t} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where C_1 (m/s) and C_2 (m/s^{1/2}) are parameters. C_1 is related to hydraulic conductivity, and C_2 is the soil sorptivity. The (unsaturated) hydraulic conductivity of the soil (k) was computed using the relationship:

$$K = \frac{C_1}{A} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where C_1 is the slope of the curve of the cumulative infiltration versus the square root of time, A is the Van Genuchten parameters.

Soil water repellency

Similar procedure as done for unsaturated hydraulic conductivity was carried out for

soil water repellency with a decagon mini disk infiltrometer at 2 cm suction. Ethanol was used instead of water to determine the repellency level. The repellency index, R as defined by (Tillman *et al.*, 1989), as the ratio of the soil – ethanol sorptivity (S_e ;cm/s^{1/2}) to the soil water sorptivity (S_w ;cm/s^{1/2}) was used to determine water repellency. The equation used was:

$$R = 1.95 \frac{S_e}{S_w} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Laboratory analyses

Soil particle-size distribution was determined using the modified hydrometer method (Bouyocous, 1962). The soil pH was determined with a digital pH meter both in water and 0.01 M CaCl₂ solution, using a 1:2 for both soil:water and soil:CaCl₂ ratios on two-way equilibrium with buffer solution at pH 4.0 and 7.0 (Pecch *et al.*, 1953). Available phosphorus (P) was extracted using the Bray-1 method (Bray and Kurtz, 1945) and was measured calorimetrically with the molybdo-phosphoric-blue method using ascorbic acid as a reducing agent (Murphy and Riley, 1962). Exchangeable calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), potassium (K) and sodium (Na) were extracted with 1 N neutral ammonium acetate solution (Thomas, 1982). Calcium, potassium and magnesium in the extracts were determined using an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer PG 990 model, while Na was determined using a flame photometer. Determination of organic carbon was done by the wet oxidation method of (Walkley and Black, 1934) as described by (Nelson and Sommers, 1982). Activation of the reaction was done by the addition of concentrated sulphuric acid as a catalyst. Micro-Kjeldahl technique as described by

(Bremner and Mulvaney, 1982) was used to determine the total nitrogen content.

Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis of all the data was performed by the analysis of variance (ANOVA) test, and statistical differences among treatment means were estimated by Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

Pre-cropping soil analysis.

The pre-cropping soil properties before burning is showing in Table 1. Values of 5.9 and 5.5 were obtained for pH using H_2O and $CaCl_2$, respectively. The results indicated that the soil pH was strongly acidic according to the classification of soil reactions by (Adepetu *et al.*, 2014). The continuous use of inorganic fertilizers led to the soil's acidity and could be pronounced in the absence of liming programme (Buol *et al.*, 2011). The available soil phosphorus prior to burning was low with value of 7.51 mg kg^{-1} (Adepetu *et al.*, 2014). The low value obtained for available soil phosphorus could be due to the fixation of Fe and Al oxides. The Fe and Al oxides are found in acidic soils. The result supported the findings of (Adepetu, 1986) who reported that over 95% of the land area of southwestern Nigeria has low to medium levels of available Phosphorus in the plough

Table 1: Chemical properties of the soil before burning.

Soil parameter	Value
pH	
H_2O	5.9
$CaCl_2$	5.5
Organic Carbon (g kg^{-1})	9.40
Total nitrogen (g kg^{-1})	3.50
Available phosphorus (mg kg^{-1})	7.51
Calcium (cmol kg^{-1})	1.17
Magnesium (cmol kg^{-1})	0.39
Potassium (cmol kg^{-1})	0.22
Sodium (cmol kg^{-1})	0.10

layer of the soil.

Soil physical properties.

Particle size distribution

The texture of the soil at the experimental site was loamy sand (Table 2). Burning did not significantly change the particle size of the soil as the textural class of the soil remained unchanged after burning. This was in agreement to the result of (Garcia-Corona *et al.*, 2004). The findings of Parise and Cannon (2012) was contrary to the result obtained. The authors reported that temperatures from 170°C and higher decreased the clay and silt particle size ratios of the soil. However, in a severely burnt soil in Nigeria, Oguntunde *et al.* (2004) noted that there was an improvement in sand content which was significant,

Table 2: Textural class of soil

Treatment	sand	silt	clay		Textural class
			silt+clay	g kg^{-1}	
Control	759	117	123	240	Loamy sand
200°C	749	120	131	251	Loamy sand
400°C	744	127	129	256	Loamy sand

correspondingly leading to a reduction in the content of clay.

Bulk density

Fire intensity have no significant effect on soil bulk density (Figure 1), although the mean values decreased from 1.18 in control to 1.17 g cm⁻³ for 400°C treatment in the first season. The second season shows mean soil bulk density values of 1.38, 1.09 and 1.24 g cm⁻³ for control, 200°C and 400°C, respectively. The results for the second season showed that at $P < 0.05$, the treatments were significant. The decreased soil bulk densities with increased fire intensities relative to the control obtained in both seasons might be due to the presence of ash from the burnt plant materials. The ash made the soil lighter thereby reducing bulk density of the soil after burning. Oguntunde *et al.* (2008) had earlier observed that bulk density reduced due to burning on the soil making the result in Figure 1 similar to their observation. However, Fernandez *et al.*, (1997) noted contrary results to the one reported in Figure 1 that bulk density increased after burning. The soil aggregation destruction and soil organic matter loss make the authors conclude that bulk density increased after burning.

Soil strength

The result (Figure 2) shows fire intensity on soil strength for the two seasons. Mean values of 7.05, 6.29, 5.99 kg m⁻² were obtained for the control, 200°C, 400°C respectively for the first season. In the second season, a similar trend was observed in which control > 200°C > 400°C with respective values of 6.35, 6.05 and 5.83 kg m⁻². The treatments during the first season

Fig 1:- Effects of intensity of burning on soil bulk density.

show significant treatment while there was none in the second season. The drop in moisture content due to rainfall break typical of weather in August (second season) may have masked the effect of fire intensity on soil strength in the second season making it less pronounced to what was observed in the first season (April). The significant difference among the treatments was due to the destruction of organic matter in the soil (Table 3). Soil organic carbon decreases with intensive cultivation of the soil coupled with burning with led to the decrease in microaggregate stability (Figure 3) and which probably changed the structure of the soil Krol *et al.* (2013) and could be responsible for the decrease in soil strength after burning. Vepraskas (1988) reported that soil strength is a function of soil structure, soil water content and cementing agent. The results for both seasons showed that soil strength reduced after burning.

Figure 2:- Effects of burning intensity on soil strength.

Microaggregate stability

Microaggregate stability of the soil after burning is highly variable across the two seasons (Figure 3). Values of 8.15, 7.02, 6.48 g kg⁻¹ were obtained respectively for control, 200°C and 400°C treatments in the first season. There was significant different in the results of the control and 400°C at $p < 0.05$. However, the differences in soil microaggregate stability was not

statistically significant in second season. The results revealed that microaggregate stability reduced after burning in the first season is probably due to a reduction in the soil organic carbon content after burning (Table 3). It could also be due to decrease in soil moisture content after burning. The variability of the result (Figure 3) obtained for both seasons in response to different levels of fire confirms the research work of Jordan et al. (2011) and Simansky et al. (2012), and it authenticates the findings of Mataix-Solera et al. (2011) that aggregate stability is a function of several factors including repellence level of soil, intensity of fire and soil organic matter.

Figure 3: Effects of burning intensity on microaggregate stability

Table 3:- Effects of fire intensity on sorptivity after burning for the first and second cropping season.

Treatment	Days after burning			Days after burning		
	1	7	42	1	7	42
	(cm hr ⁻¹)			(cm hr ⁻¹)		
	Season One			Season Two		
Control	46.4a	125.5a	59.0a	53.6a	123.8a	178.6b
200°C	73.8a	85.1ab	64.1a	50.7a	35.3b	461.8a
400°C	68.9a	27.5b	94.5a	11.3b	44.7b	372.2a

Means in the same column with the same alphabets are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Sorptivity.

The results for sorptivity after burning shows high level of variability (Table 3). The table showed an insignificant increase in sorptivity immediately after burning for fire intensities 200°C and 400°C in the first season. In the second season, there was significant reduction in sorptivity immediately after burning for fire intensities 400°C and 200°C with mean values of 50.7 and 11.3 cm hr⁻¹ respectively. This may be due to ash particles blocking the pores at the soil surface (DeBano *et al.*, 2005), thereby leading to low soil wettability (DeBano, 2000), ultimately resulting in surface runoff of soil (Cerda and Doerr, 2008). On the seventh day after burning, the sorptivity of fire intensities 400°C and 200°C reduced significantly for both seasons when compared to the control. It follows the trend of control > 400°C > 200°C. The results on the forty second day changed for the second season with significant increment of the sorptivity of fire intensities 400°C and 200°C when compared to the control. (Woods and Balfour, 2008) reported that ash increased infiltration of soils after burning which may have led to the increase in sorptivity of the fire intensities.

Soil water repellency

Soil water repellency after burning was not statistically significant ($P < 0.05$) for all the treatments on all the days for the first and second seasons (Table 4). Soil organic carbon have been reported to have a major influence on water repellency (Bryant *et al.*, 2005). In this study, organic carbon was not significantly different among all the treatments (Table 6). Therefore, the insignificant difference among the treatments applied on soil water repellency could be linked to soil organic carbon (Table 6). Duration of burning is another factor that has been identified to influence water repellency. Neris *et al.* (2013) reported that the longer the duration of burning, the more the soil will be repellent. In this study, duration of burning occurred for few minutes and this may have limited the repellency (Table 4).

Unsaturated hydraulic conductivity

Unsaturated hydraulic conductivity increased after burning for both seasons (Table 5) though not statistically significant. This could be due to the fire intensities which are classified to be of low and moderate intensities (Certini, 2005). These classes of intensities usually produce

Table 4:- Effects of fire intensity on water repellency after burning for the first and second cropping season

Treatment	Days after burning			Days after burning		
	1	7	42	1	7	42
	← (cm s ⁻¹) →			← (cm s ⁻¹) →		
	Season one			Season two		
Control	2.49a	2.50a	3.52a	9.03a	2.41a	3.29a
200°C	38.30a	8.39a	5.67a	14.39a	5.68a	1.19a
400°C	7.05a	28.45a	2.87a	27.80a	5.22a	1.52a

Means in the same column with the same alphabets are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

black ashes whereas white ashes produced from high intensities have been reported to have a temporal impact on soil hydraulic properties (Pereira *et al.*, 2012). Therefore the production of black ashes in this study could be the reason while the unsaturated hydraulic conductivity was not significant among all the treatments after burning (Table 5).

Chemical properties

Soil pH

The influence of burning on soil pH for the first and second seasons are shown in Table 6 and 7 respectively. For the first season, the pH values of both temperatures were higher significantly ($p < 0.05$) more than the unburned soil with figures 5.3, 6.9, and 7.3 for the Control, 200°C and 400°C, respectively. The increase in pH across both temperatures could be due to the presence of ash which usually accompany burning (Molina *et al.*, 2007). The results observed in this study also supported that of Boerner *et al.* (2009) likewise that of Aref *et al.* (2011) whose report said soil pH after forest fire results into an increment in general. However (Certini, 2005) observed increase

in soil pH significantly following burning mainly at temperatures between 450°C to 500°C. This might be the reason why the mean results of pH at both temperatures statistically showed no significance from the control in the second burning season (Table 4) with values of 5.6, 6.9 and 6.5 for the Control, 200°C and 400°C respectively. Further, the results obtained for both seasons supported the results of (Pereira *et al.*, 2011) that soil pH increased immediately after severe slash or debris burning.

Total nitrogen

The mean total soil nitrogen contents for the treatments are presented in Tables 6 and 7 respectively at first season and at season two. The results showed no significant effect of burning on soil Nitrogen. This was similar to the observation of Nkana *et al.* (1996) that wood ash rarely contained Nitrogen and during its application would hardly lead to any effect on the soil Nitrogen. However, obtained results were contrary to the findings of Murphy *et al.* (2006) that most short-term effects of bush burning were mostly significant leading to

Table 5:- Effects of fire intensity on unsaturated hydraulic conductivity at 2 cm after burning for the first and second cropping season.

Treatment	Days after burning			Days after burning		
	1	7	42	1	7	42
	(cm hr ⁻¹)			(cm hr ⁻¹)		
	Season one			Season two		
Control	4.85a	12.33a	7.74a	5.11a	3.22a	11.26a
200°C	12.33a	8.37a	13.55a	4.52a	2.55a	13.63a
400°C	9.08a	1.15a	15.41a	3.89a	4.19a	11.30a

Means in the same column with the same alphabets are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Table 6:- Mean values of chemical properties of soil burned at control, 200°C and 400°C for the first season

Soil parameter	Control	200°C	400°C
pH (water)	5.6b	7.3a	7.8a
pH (CaCl ₂)	5.3b	6.9a	7.3a
Organic Carbon (g kg ⁻¹)	19.1a	15.7a	14.4a
Total Nitrogen (g kg ⁻¹)	3.62a	3.58a	3.57a
Available Phosphorus (mg kg ⁻¹)	10.25a	14.41a	12.56a
Calcium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	1.29a	1.25a	1.40a
Magnesium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.55a	0.60a	0.58a
Potassium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.38b	0.54a	0.58a
Sodium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.12b	0.32a	0.39a

Means in the same row with the same alphabets are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

Table 7:- Mean values of chemical properties of soil burned at control, 200°C and 400°C in the second season.

Soil parameter	Control	200°C	400°C
pH (water)	5.9a	7.3a	7.0a
pH (CaCl ₂)	5.6a	6.9a	6.5a
Organic Carbon (g kg ⁻¹)	15.2a	14.3a	14.2a
Total Nitrogen (g kg ⁻¹)	4.62a	5.25a	4.10a
Available Phosphorus (mg kg ⁻¹)	8.99a	10.85a	12.67a
Calcium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	10.19b	11.96a	11.48ab
Magnesium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	1.69b	2.91a	2.99a
Potassium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.29c	1.20b	1.57a
Sodium (cmol kg ⁻¹)	0.54b	0.78a	0.76a

Means in the same row with the same alphabets are not significantly different at 0.05 level of probability according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test.

increase leaching of mineral forms of Nitrogen, Sulphur and Phosphorus in the soil solution concentrations.

Organic carbon

Soil organic carbon contents after burning for the first and second seasons reduced insignificantly (Table 6 and 7). No differences were obtained in the first burning season while control had the highest value of 15.2 g kg⁻¹ followed by 400°C and 200°C, respectively, with values of 14.3 and 14.2 g kg⁻¹ in the second season (Table 4). The insignificant differences

among the treatment could be as a result of the time in which the controlled bush burning took place. For both seasons, the burning took place for fifteen minutes and the soil samples were taken from the field 48 hours after burning. Following wildfires, the length of climate and time largely drive the magnitude effect of wildfires on soil properties including chemical properties. In a study in Guizhou Province, Southwest China, it was reported by Zhang et al. (1999) that soil chemical properties including soil organic matter, total Nitrogen, available Phosphorus and

Potassium two to four months increased significantly in an artificial *P. massoniana* forest after a wildfire.

Available phosphorus

There was no significant change in the available soil P with burning in both seasons (Table 6 and 7). There was however a consistent increase in the soil available P contents with burning in both seasons. During fires of high severity Ogundele et al. (2011) reported that the total phosphorus that might be lost to volatilization could be between fifty to sixty percent and of this volatilized phosphorus, some of it ends up as available phosphorus that have been increased following burning in both the soil and ash. In Southeast Asia, Tanaka et al. (2004) also reported that exchangeable bases and available phosphorus increases in contents influenced by the fire intensity. All treatments in Table 7 have greater values than the threshold limit of 8 mg kg⁻¹ proposed by (Kang et al., 1980).

Exchangeable bases

Concentrations of exchangeable bases after burning for both seasons increased (Table 6 and 7). In the first season, exchangeable potassium and sodium significantly increased at $P < 0.05$ in the 200°C and 400°C plots when compared to the Control plot with exchangeable potassium mean values of 0.38, 0.54 and 0.58 cmol kg⁻¹ for Control, 200°C and 400°C, respectively. For exchangeable sodium the mean values were 0.12, 0.32 and 0.39 cmol kg⁻¹ for control, 200°C and 400°C, respectively. Similar trends were observed for the second burning season for exchangeable potassium and exchangeable sodium (Table 7). Increased exchangeable potassium after burning at all temperatures in the soil had earlier been

reported by (Iwuafor et al., 2000).

The exchangeable Calcium and exchangeable Magnesium contents in all the treatments were non- statistically different even though the values increased with intensity of burning during the first season (Table 6). The results obtained in this study were similar to the findings of Opara-Nadi et al. (2010) that non - combustible elements such as calcium, magnesium, potassium and sodium when compared to the control have high concentrations on the burnt soil surface. The increases in concentrations of these exchangeable cations after burning make the soil suitable for crop production because the plant roots have access to the cations which are available following burning. Giardina et al. (2000) observed exchangeable calcium and potassium after burning was higher. The values obtained for Calcium in Table 7 for all the treatment is higher than the recommended threshold value of 5 cmolkg⁻¹ by Marx et al., (1996) in most crops. Table 7 shows an increase in Magnesium after burning over the threshold value of 2 cmolkg⁻¹ for most crops as reported by (Schwartz and Coralles, 1989). The increments were attributed to degradation of soil organic matter at high temperatures and long duration of burning.

Conclusion

This study shows that controlled bush burning improved soil available phosphorus, pH, and exchangeable cations while bulk density, soil strength, water dispersible clay, organic carbon and total nitrogen decreased. Controlled burning was able to increase soil exchangeable Calcium and Magnesium to a range optimum for most crops without fertilizer supplements in contrast to the unburnt plots.

Sorptivity decreased significantly after controlled bush burning while it had no significant effect on unsaturated hydraulic conductivity and on soil water repellency. Consequently, it is concluded that controlled bush burning could have transient positive effects on some selected soil properties immediately after burning.

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